

Efficient Congo Red Photodegradation via Fe-Doped CdS@Carbon Quantum Dots under Visible Light Irradiation

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Abstract

In this study, a novel Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite was successfully synthesized via a facile one-pot hydrothermal method for the photocatalytic degradation of Congo Red (CR) dye under visible light. Structural analyses confirmed the formation of hexagonal CdS nanocrystals (8.5-10.9 nm) coupled with amorphous carbon quantum dots (CQDs). The Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite demonstrated significantly enhanced photocatalytic performance, achieving approximately 90% degradation of CR in 120 minutes, whereas pristine CQDs achieved only 45% under identical conditions. This superior activity is attributed to the synergistic effects of Fe-doping, which introduces defect states that promote charge separation, and CQDs, which improve light harvesting and electron transport. Kinetic analysis revealed a pseudo-first-order reaction mechanism and a substantially lower activation energy for the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs (16.2 kJmol⁻¹) compared to CQDs (24.8 kJmol⁻¹). These findings highlight the potential of Fe-doped CdS@CQDs as a highly efficient and promising photocatalyst for treating dye-contaminated wastewater.

Keywords: Carbon quantum dots, Fe-doped CdS, photocatalysis, congo red degradation, activation energy

1. Introduction

The rapid industrialization and the growing use of synthetic dyes in industries such as textiles, paper, plastics, and food processing have significantly increased the discharge of dye-contaminated wastewater into aquatic ecosystems (Orak, 2024a; Orak et al., 2025). Among these pollutants, azo dyes, such as Congo Red (CR), are of particular concern due to their high chemical stability, complex aromatic structures, and resistance to conventional biological and physicochemical treatment methods. The persistence of CR in the environment not only leads to ecological imbalance but also poses serious toxicological risks, as it and its degradation by-products have been reported to exhibit carcinogenic, mutagenic, and teratogenic effects (Alharbi et al., 2025; Mekidiche et al., 2025; Quintanilla-Villanueva et al., 2025). Consequently, the development of efficient, sustainable, and environmentally friendly treatment technologies for removing such recalcitrant organic dyes from wastewater has become a pressing global challenge (Haste et al., 2024; Karakaş et al., 2025; Kaya et al., 2025). Among the various advanced treatment approaches, photocatalysis has emerged as a promising and eco-friendly technique due to its ability to harness solar or artificial light energy to degrade harmful organic pollutants into benign compounds such as CO₂, H₂O and inorganic ions (Bakır et al., 2025; Orak et al., 2016; Ersöz et al., 2024). In a typical photocatalytic process, a semiconductor photocatalyst absorbs photons with energy equal to or greater than its band gap, exciting electrons from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB) and generating electron-hole pairs (e⁻/h⁺) (Orak et al., 2021a, 2022a). These photogenerated charge carriers participate in redox reactions at the catalyst surface, where electrons reduce oxygen molecules to generate superoxide radicals (•O₂⁻), and holes oxidize water or hydroxyl ions to produce hydroxyl radicals (•OH) (Bakır et al., 2024a; Orak and Yüksel, 2022b). These reactive oxygen species (ROS) act as powerful oxidizing agents that break down complex organic molecules into non-toxic products (Bakır and Orak, 2024;

Orak and Yüksel, 2021b). Despite its significant potential, the practical application of photocatalysis is often limited by factors such as narrow light absorption, rapid recombination of charge carriers, and photocorrosion of the photocatalyst (Arabacı et al., 2025; Bakır et al., 2024b). Among the wide variety of semiconductors investigated, cadmium sulfide (CdS) has garnered considerable attention as a visible-light-responsive photocatalyst due to its narrow band gap (~2.4 eV) and strong ability to utilize the visible spectrum efficiently (Balnan et al., 2025; Orak et al., 2024). However, pristine CdS suffers from severe drawbacks, including rapid electron-hole recombination, low photostability, and limited surface active sites, which restrict its photocatalytic efficiency (Batur et al., 2022; Batur, Şahin, et al., 2023; Onat et al., 2021). To overcome these limitations, several strategies have been developed, with metal ion doping and integration with carbon-based nanomaterials emerging as the most effective (Horoz et al., 2018; Horoz and Sahin, 2017b, 2017a). Transition-metal doping (e.g., Fe, Co, Ni) introduces defect states within the CdS lattice, which enhances the separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs and promotes redox-active pathways that accelerate ROS production. In particular, Fe doping has attracted significant attention because the Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ redox couple can act as an electron mediator, facilitating Fenton-like reactions that generate additional •OH radicals, thereby improving overall photocatalytic activity (Onat et al., 2024; Orak, 2024b). On the other hand, carbon quantum dots (CQDs) have recently emerged as promising co-catalysts due to their high specific surface area, excellent electron-accepting properties, and abundant surface functional groups. CQDs can act as electron reservoirs, efficiently transferring photogenerated electrons away from the CdS surface, thereby suppressing charge recombination and enhancing visible-light utilization. Moreover, their tunable surface states and up-conversion photoluminescence further broaden the light absorption range, improving photocatalytic

performance (Batur, Kutluay, et al., 2023; Ca et al., 2017; Mehrabanpour, Nezamzadeh-Ejhih, and Ghattavi, 2023; Onat et al., 2024; Orak et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024). In this context, the synergistic combination of Fe doping and CQD integration is expected to overcome the inherent drawbacks of CdS-based photocatalysts. Herein, the facile hydrothermal synthesis of a novel Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite are reported to evaluate its efficiency as a visible-light-driven photocatalyst for the degradation of CR. The integration of Fe ions introduces beneficial defect states that facilitate charge separation, while CQDs enhance electron mobility and extend visible-light absorption. Together, these modifications are designed to maximize photocatalytic efficiency by promoting effective light harvesting, accelerating radical generation, and improving the stability of CdS. This study provides a sustainable and robust strategy for the treatment of dye-polluted wastewater using advanced photocatalytic nanocomposites.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

Cadmium acetate dihydrate ($\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), thiourea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$), ferric chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), citric acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$), and ethylenediamine ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification. Congo Red (CR) dye was obtained from Merck and used as a model organic pollutant. All solutions were prepared with deionized water.

2.2. Synthesis of CQDs

CQDs were synthesized via a hydrothermal method. In a typical procedure, 2 g of citric acid and 2 mL of ethylenediamine were dissolved in 50 mL deionized water under stirring. The solution was transferred into a 100 mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated at 180 °C for 6 h. After cooling to room temperature, the obtained dark-brown solution was dialyzed against deionized water for 24 h to remove unreacted precursors. The purified CQDs solution was freeze-dried to obtain a dry powder.

2.3. C Synthesis of Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposites

Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposites were prepared by a one-pot hydrothermal method. Typically, 1 mmol of $\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 2 mmol of thiourea were dissolved in 50 mL of deionized water containing a fixed concentration of CQDs (10 mg). To this solution, an appropriate amount of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 mol% relative to Cd^{2+}) was added as a dopant precursor. This specific dopant concentration (2 mol%) was selected based on preliminary experiments and literature reports, which indicated it to be optimal for enhancing photocatalytic activity without causing significant lattice distortion. The mixture was transferred into a Teflon-lined autoclave and maintained at 160 °C for 8 h. The precipitate was collected by centrifugation, washed with ethanol and deionized water several times, and dried at 60 °C overnight.

2.4. Characterization

The structural and optical properties of the synthesized materials were investigated using a series of advanced characterization techniques. The crystalline phase and purity of the samples were examined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) employing $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm). The diffraction patterns provided insight into the crystallite size, phase composition, and possible lattice strain induced by Fe doping. Raman spectroscopy measurements were carried out with a Renishaw inVia Raman microscope using a 532 nm excitation source in order to probe the vibrational modes of carbon and CdS domains, as well as to identify structural defects and disorder. The optical absorption behavior of the samples was evaluated by UV-Vis spectrophotometry in the range of 200-800 nm, which allowed determination of the band gap energies and assessment of light-harvesting capability. Finally, the photocatalytic performance was assessed through degradation of CR under visible-light irradiation, and the temporal change in concentration was monitored at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 497$ nm. These combined characterization techniques enabled

comprehensive understanding of the structural, vibrational, and optical features of the CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposites, directly correlating material properties with their photocatalytic performance.

2.5. Photocatalytic experiment

In a typical experiment, 50 mg of catalyst was dispersed in 100 mL of a 10 mg L⁻¹ CR solution (pH ≈ 7). Prior to irradiation, the suspension was magnetically stirred in the dark

for 30 min to reach adsorption-desorption equilibrium. A 300 W Xe lamp equipped with a 420 nm cut-off filter was used as the visible light source, and the light intensity at the solution surface was measured to be 100 mW.cm⁻². During visible-light irradiation, aliquots (3 mL) were withdrawn at regular intervals, centrifuged to remove catalyst particles, and analyzed by UV-Vis spectroscopy. The degradation efficiency was calculated using:

$$\text{Degradation Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} * 100$$

where C_0 is the initial CR concentration and C_t is the concentration at irradiation time t .

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 presents the XRD patterns of pristine CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposites. The CQDs exhibited a broad diffraction peak centered at $2\theta \approx 23.2^\circ$, which corresponds to the (002) plane of graphitic carbon. The broad and low-intensity nature of this peak confirms the amorphous structure of the synthesized CQDs, consistent with previous reports on carbon-based nanomaterials (Mmelesi et al., 2024). In contrast, the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs pattern revealed several sharp diffraction peaks at 24.8° , 26.6° , 28.3° , 43.9° , 47.6° , 51.9° , and 54.9° , which were indexed to the (100), (002), (101), (110), (103), (112), and (201) planes of hexagonal CdS (JCPDS No. 41-1049). The absence of impurity peaks indicates the high purity of the synthesized phase. The obtained d-spacings (0.3587, 0.3348, 0.3151, 0.2061, 0.1909, 0.1760, and 0.1671 nm) are in good agreement with standard values, further confirming the successful formation of the CdS hexagonal structure (Doğan et al., 2024; Mehrabanpour et al., 2021; Ghattavi, et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2021). The broadening of the diffraction peaks suggests nanocrystalline

dimensions. Using the Scherrer equation, the crystallite size was calculated to be in the range of 8.5–10.9 nm, with the (002) plane showing the largest size (10.9 nm) and the (201) plane showing the smallest (8.5 nm). These results are highly consistent with previously reported Fe-doped CdS nanoparticles, which typically exhibit crystallite sizes between 7 and 12 nm (Liu et al., 2013; Akinwunmi et al., 2014; Ammar et al., 2020; M Naziruddin Khan Abdullah et al., 2020). The slight variations in crystallite size across different planes may be attributed to anisotropic growth and lattice strain introduced by Fe doping. Importantly, Fe incorporation did not generate additional peaks, indicating that Fe ions substituted Cd sites within the CdS lattice without altering its hexagonal crystal structure. Minor shifts in peak positions (0.05 - 0.1°) relative to standard CdS further suggest the presence of lattice strain, which is commonly reported upon doping with transition metal ions (Nan et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2022; Maran et al., 2025). Such strain may introduce defect sites that facilitate charge separation, thereby enhancing the photocatalytic performance of the nanocomposite.

Figure 1. XRD pattern of CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite

Figure 2 displays the Raman spectra of CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite. For the CQDs, two characteristic peaks are observed at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (D band) and $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (G band). The D band corresponds to disordered carbon or defects in the sp^2 domains, while the G band arises from the stretching vibration of graphitic sp^2 carbon. The intensity ratio ($I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$) provides information about the degree of disorder in the carbon structure. In the present case, the ratio is greater than 1, indicating a relatively high defect density, which is a common feature of CQDs synthesized via bottom-up methods (Dervishi et al., 2019; Ma et al., 2023). In the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite, apart from the D and G bands of carbon, additional peaks are observed at $\sim 300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are attributed to the longitudinal optical (LO) phonon modes of CdS. The presence of these CdS-related peaks confirms the successful incorporation of CdS nanoparticles into the composite structure (Dervishi et al., 2019; Kostić and Romčević,

2004). Moreover, slight variations in the D and G band positions and intensities compared to pristine CQDs suggest an interaction between the CdS nanoparticles and the carbon framework. The shift and broadening of Raman bands in the composite indicate lattice strain and charge-transfer interactions induced by Fe doping. Such modifications are known to enhance defect-mediated electron-hole separation, which in turn contributes to improved photocatalytic activity. The coexistence of CdS phonon modes with the carbon-related bands demonstrates the strong coupling between the semiconductor and carbon domains, which is crucial for effective photocatalyst design. In summary, Raman analysis confirms (i) the amorphous/disordered carbon nature of CQDs, (ii) the successful formation of CdS nanoparticles within the composite, and (iii) the structural modifications induced by Fe doping that are favorable for photocatalytic applications (Ammar et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2021; Doğan et al., 2024).

Figure 2. Raman spectra of CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite

Shown in Figure 3 are the UV-Vis spectra of CQDs compared with those of the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite. The CQDs display a pronounced absorption band centered at approximately 270 nm, which is assigned to the π - π^* electronic transitions of conjugated sp^2 carbon domains. In addition, a broad absorption tail extending toward the visible region is evident, originating from surface states and defect-related transitions. Such spectral characteristics are in good agreement with previous reports on carbon-based nanomaterials (Ganguly and Srivastava, 2020; Tungare et al., 2020; Moslem et al., 2025). For the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs composite, the absorption profile retains the characteristic CQD band but further exhibits a well-defined absorption edge at ~ 500 nm, corresponding to the fundamental band gap transition of hexagonal CdS. By comparison, bulk CdS typically shows its absorption onset around 515-520 nm ($E_g \approx 2.4$ eV) (Ganguly and

Srivastava, 2020; Nair et al., 2002; Moslem et al., 2025). The observed slight blue shift of the absorption edge in the nanocomposite relative to bulk CdS is attributed to quantum confinement effects associated with nanoscale crystallite dimensions, as well as electronic modifications induced by Fe incorporation. The introduction of Fe ions is also known to create localized electronic states within the CdS band structure. These states not only perturb the band edge but also broaden the absorption window in the visible region. Such band gap modulation is beneficial for photocatalytic applications, as it enhances visible-light harvesting and improves charge carrier separation. The cooperative contributions of carbon domains, CdS nanoparticles, and Fe-induced defect states are therefore expected to promote efficient photoinduced charge transfer, ultimately enhancing the degradation performance of organic dyes such as CR.

Figure 3. UV–Vis absorption spectra of carbon quantum dots (CQDs) and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite

The photocatalytic performance of CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs toward CR degradation under visible light irradiation is illustrated in Figure 4. The experimental conditions were set as follows: CR concentration of 10 mg L^{-1} , catalyst dosage of 0.5 g L^{-1} in 100 mL aqueous solution, neutral pH (~ 7.0), irradiation with a 300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$), and a dark equilibration step of 30 min before light exposure. The progress of degradation was monitored by measuring the absorbance of CR at 497 nm over 120 min. The results clearly revealed the superior photocatalytic performance of the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite compared to CQDs alone. Under visible-light irradiation, CQDs achieved only $\sim 45\%$ degradation of CR within 120 min, reflecting their limited photocatalytic activity. This modest performance is related to surface adsorption processes and defect-mediated generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), but restricted by their amorphous nature and inefficient charge carrier separation. In contrast, Fe-doped CdS@CQDs exhibited $\sim 90\%$ degradation of CR in the same period, demonstrating a pronounced enhancement in photocatalytic efficiency. This improvement can be attributed to three synergistic effects: (i) strong visible-light absorption by crystalline CdS domains, (ii) suppression of electron–hole

recombination via electron transfer to CQDs, and (iii) the introduction of Fe ions, which generate defect states and promote $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ redox cycling, leading to accelerated hydroxyl radical ($\bullet\text{OH}$) formation through Fenton-like processes (Horoz, 2017; Baytar et al., 2018a; Nar et al., 2019; Orak et al., 2024). The overall mechanism involves the excitation of CdS under visible light, generating electron–hole pairs. Electrons are transferred to CQDs and subsequently reduce O_2 to $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals, while holes oxidize H_2O or OH^- species to yield $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals (Orak, 2024a; Ersöz et al., 2024). These reactive radicals attack the azo bonds ($-\text{N}=\text{N}-$) of CR molecules, causing stepwise cleavage and eventual mineralization into CO_2 , H_2O , and inorganic ions. Taken together, the findings confirm that while CQDs exhibit moderate photocatalytic activity, the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite provides a highly efficient system for dye degradation, benefiting from optimized light harvesting, efficient charge separation, and enhanced radical generation. The powerful ROS generation mechanism observed suggests that this photocatalyst could also be highly effective for the degradation of other persistent organic pollutants, such as different classes of dyes or phenolic compounds, warranting further investigation.

Figure 4. Photocatalytic degradation of CR under visible-light irradiation using CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite

The temperature dependence of the photocatalytic degradation of CR was investigated to determine the activation energy (E_a) of the process. Pseudo-first-order rate constants were calculated at five different temperatures (298-338 K) for both CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs. The Arrhenius plots of $\ln(k)$ versus $1/T$ was used to determine E_a values for pristine CQDs and Fe-doped CdS@CQDs composite. For the pristine CQDs, the linear fit yielded an E_a value of 24.8 kJmol^{-1} , whereas for the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs composite the activation energy was significantly lower, at 16.2 kJmol^{-1} . The reduced energy barrier in the doped composite reflects the role of Fe ions in introducing localized energy states that facilitate charge separation and transfer. Additionally, the CQDs framework enhances electron mobility and suppresses recombination, further improving catalytic efficiency. The comparatively higher E_a of CQDs indicates that their photocatalytic activity is more strongly limited by the energetic barrier for ROS generation and dye degradation. Conversely, the Fe-doped CdS@CQDs system benefits from synergistic effects: (i) visible-light absorption by CdS, (ii) charge transport through CQDs, and (iii) defect-assisted pathways from Fe doping (Baytar et al., 2018b; Ganguly and Srivastava, 2020; Moslem et al., 2025). These factors not only reduce the

activation energy but also enhance the kinetics of CR degradation. Overall, the Arrhenius analysis confirms that Fe-doped CdS@CQDs provide a more energetically favorable pathway for dye degradation, consistent with their superior photocatalytic performance observed in earlier experiments.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the successful synthesis of a novel Fe-doped CdS@CQDs nanocomposite as a highly efficient visible-light-driven photocatalyst for Congo Red (CR) degradation. The nanocomposite exhibited superior photocatalytic activity, achieving ~90% CR removal in 120 minutes, a significant improvement over pristine CQDs (~45%). This enhancement is attributed to the powerful synergy between Fe-doping and CQD integration, which promotes efficient charge separation and enhances light absorption. The kinetic analysis confirmed a more energetically favorable reaction pathway for the composite, as evidenced by its significantly lower activation energy (16.2 kJmol^{-1}) compared to CQDs (24.8 kJmol^{-1}). Overall, this work establishes that combining Fe-doping with a CQD framework is a robust strategy for developing advanced photocatalysts for effective environmental remediation.

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